

NICOLAUS COPERNICUS UNIVERSITY

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

Anti-discrimination provisions are now more often included in higher education institutions' (HEI) policies than they were a few years ago. While the process of counteracting gender-based violence (GBV) in Polish academia started in 2010 with the establishment of the Rector's Committee for Preventing Discrimination at the University of Warsaw,¹ in recent years, many Polish universities have adopted measures designed to counteract discrimination in the workplace. They are usually part of the HEIs' internal regulations,^{2,3} but there are exceptions to this rule. Some more progressive HEIs develop and implement (internal) anti-mobbing and anti-discrimination procedures. On the one hand, this trend is an effect of the European Union's policies (i.e. the European Charter & Code for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers) and funding programmes (i.e. Horizon 2020), which aim to foster gender equality change by facilitating the development and implementation of gender equality measures and plans in Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) (for example, GENERA, ACT, and MindTheGEP projects carried out at the Jagiellonian University in Krakow).^{4,5} On the other hand, publicising cases of discrimination against employees or students and reports confirming the existence of harassment at Polish public universities^{6,7,8} has resulted in the development of preventive actions to ensure the safety and security of RPO communities. In addition, the Ombudsperson had made several official appeals to the Conference of Rectors of Academic Schools in Poland (CRASP) and many ministries of the Polish government (i.e. in 2016 and 2019) and has asked them to adopt programmes to ensure the implementation of internal anti-discrimination procedures, and to take

¹ Fuszara, M. (2012). *Raport z prac Komisji Rektorskiej ds. Przeciwdziałania Dyskryminacji w kadencji 2008 – 2012*. Warszawa: Uniwersytet Warszawski. <http://www.rownowazni.uw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/sprawozdanie-komisji-2008-2012.docx/>

² Sierpowski, P. (2020, January 24). *Tackling gender inequalities at universities in Poland*. Gender Equality in Central and Eastern Europe Community of Practice. <https://geincee.act-on-gender.eu/Blog/tackling-gender-inequalities-universities-poland>.

³ Teutsch A., Stoch, M., & Kozakoszczak, A. (2017a). *Ramy prawne zjawiska dyskryminacji i przemocy motywowanej uprzedzeniami oraz możliwości reakcji na nie z wykorzystaniem instrumentów prawnych*. Kraków: Fundacja Autonomia. <https://bezpieczni.uj.edu.pl/documents/136167082/13991933>.

⁴ Krzaklewska, E., Sekuła, P., Struzik, J. & Ciaputa, E. (2019). *Działania na rzecz równości płci w nauce. Determinanty nierówności i narzędzia zmiany*. *Alma Mater 208-209*, 60-62.

⁵ EIGE. (2020). *Gender mainstreaming. Poland*. EIGE. <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/countries/poland>.

⁶ RPO. (2018). *Doświadczenie molestowania wśród studentek i studentów. Analiza i zalecenia*. Warszawa: Biuro Rzecznika Praw Obywatelskich. <https://www.rpo.gov.pl/sites/default/files/Do%20C5%9Bwiadczanie%20molestowania%20w%C5%9Br%C3%B3d%20studentek%20i%20student%C3%B3w%2C%202018.pdf>.

⁷ Gerlich, J. (2019). *Molestowanie na polskich uczelniach publicznych*. Warszawa: Helsińska Fundacja Praw Człowieka. <https://www.hfhr.pl/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/%E2%80%9EMolestowanie-na-polskich-uczelniach-publicznych%E2%80%9D-%E2%80%93-raport-HFPC.pdf>.

⁸ Gerlich, J., Jarzmus, K. (2020). *„Być albo nie być” – pracowniczki i pracownicy polskich instytucji artystycznych wobec zagrożenia mobbingiem, molestowaniem i molestowaniem seksualnym*. Warszawa: Helsińska Fundacja Praw Człowieka. <https://www.hfhr.pl/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/byc-albo-nie-byc-21-11.pdf>.

active preventive measures against harassment.^{9,10} Nevertheless, the number of universities with anti-discrimination measures, policies, or procedures in place is still rather small compared to the total number of HEIs in Poland. Finally, GBV in higher education and RPOs is still a taboo topic,¹¹ and as a result there are no specific prosecution or disciplinary measures and no services provided to victims by HEIs.

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń (NCU) provides its community with documents that address the issue of discrimination from both a more general and a more detailed perspective. General provisions on the obligation to respect the norms of equal treatment, anti-discrimination, and anti-harassment in any form in relation to students, co-workers, and subordinates, and on the disciplinary liability of academic teachers, students, and PhD candidates in the case of violations of the university's rules are included in the university's Ethical Code of Employees (2017)¹² and in the Statute (2019),¹³ respectively. Nevertheless, several paragraphs included in the Work Regulations of Nicolaus University in Toruń (hereinafter the Work Regulations) and Order No. 209 of the Rector of Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń of 12 October 2021 on Proceedings in the Case of a Violation of the Principle of Equal Treatment at Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń (hereinafter Order No. 209) address gender-based discrimination in particular. This vignette focuses on those two policy documents.

The main actors obliged to prevent discrimination and to develop, implement, monitor, and evaluate anti-discrimination policy include: the leadership of the university and faculties (rector, deans), administrative departments and staff (i.e. Human Resources, University Centre for Support and Personal Development, Student Counselling Centre for Equality #Inclusive), thematic committees (i.e. Ethical Code Commission, Disciplinary Commissions and Department Commission for Counteracting Sexual Abuse, Mobbing and Discrimination at the Medical Faculty), and equality bodies or the equivalent (i.e. equal treatment officer, deputy rector for student and doctoral student safety, and the academic ombudsperson).

URLs

- › Work Regulations: <https://www.umk.pl/uczelnia/dokumenty/statut/Statut-UMK.pdf>
- › Order No. 209: Not available online.

Entry into force: The Work Regulations came into effect in 2019 and Order No. 209 in 2021.

⁹ Teutsch A., Stoch, M., & Kozakoszczak, A. (2017b). *Opracowanie merytoryczne na temat przeciwdziałania dyskryminacji i przemocy motywowanej uprzedzeniami dla studentów, studentek, doktorantów, doktorantek, nauczycieli i nauczycielek szkół wyższych*. Kraków: Fundacja Autonomia.

¹⁰ RPO. (2019, October). Polskie uczelnie powinny skuteczniej walczyć z molestowaniem. *Biuletyn Informacji Publicznej RPO*. <https://bip.brpo.gov.pl/pl/content/rpo-polskie-uczelnie-powinny-skuteczniej-walczyz-z-molestowaniem>

¹¹ ERAC Standing Working Group on Gender in Research and Innovation. (2020). *Sexual Harassment in the Research and Higher Education Sector: National Policies and Measures in EU Member States and Associated Countries*. Brussels: European Research Area And Innovation Committee. https://genderaction.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/SWGGR1_Sexual-Harassment-in-the-Research-Higher-Ed.-National-Policies-Measures.pdf.

¹² *Ethical Code of Nicolaus Copernicus University Employees*. (2017). Toruń: UMK. <https://www.umk.pl/en/university/excellence-in-research/Appendix-2.pdf>.

¹³ *Statute of the Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń*. (2019). Toruń: UMK. <https://www.umk.pl/uczelnia/dokumenty/statut/Statut-UMK.pdf>.

TRAINING

Anti-discrimination trainings designed to prevent discrimination are organised online and free of charge for administrative and research employees, students, and PhD candidates.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

In 2012-2017, the NCU included gender studies among its post-graduate programmes on offer, and this programme included topics concerning GBV in its curriculum (Studia Gender UMK). Currently, the university offers students many courses in which discrimination and GBV are covered or are the main topic. The courses are not compulsory but are available at different faculties and levels of study.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The two policies jointly cover **four** forms of violence: GBV, psychological violence, sexual harassment, and gender-based harassment. Both policies cover sexual harassment and gender-based harassment, while the Work Regulations also cover psychological violence and use the term GBV.

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harrassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harrassment | |

7Ps covered: Combined, the two policies cover **5Ps** – prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, and policies. Both cover prosecution, while ORDER No. 209 covers prevalence, protection and policies, and the Work Regulations cover prevention. Neither of them cover provision of services or partnerships.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups: Two target groups are addressed explicitly in both policies: academic staff and non-academic staff. Students are not addressed.

Intersectionality addressed

No

Specific vulnerable groups

Not defined

Bystanders addressed: No.

Role of perpetrators addressed: Order No. 209 addresses perpetrators in the sense that they are obliged to prove their innocence.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: Yes. The Work Regulations do not use indicators, but Order No. 209 does. Concretely, it has an indicator for prevalence: the equal treatment officer is required to report on case proceedings by submitting reports on its activities every year.

Monitoring: No.

Evaluation: Information not available.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

Order No. 209 specifies procedures, but the Work Regulations do not. Order No. 209 has **one procedure for all**.

The policy defines: Who to contact, how to report, the investigation procedure, a time frame, responsible persons/units, and outcomes.

Who to contact and how to report: A case of unequal treatment can be reported by a person who works or studies at the university or participates in any other form of education at the university. Reports of cases of unequal treatment are submitted to the officer for equal treatment. Reports can be made in any form: verbally, by phone, or in writing, which includes via electronic communication tools. Whoever reports the case of unequal treatment must substantiate their claims.

Responsible persons/units: The equal treatment officer identifies the allegations reported and assesses the evidence for those allegations. If the equal treatment officer finds the application justified, he or she undertakes actions aimed at clarifying the matter. Applications that the officer for equal treatment deems unjustified will not be examined. If the application indicates circumstances that justify action being taken by other entities, in particular the Anti-Mobbing Committee, the academic spokesperson, or the deputy for the safety of students and doctoral

students, the officer for equal treatment submits the application to the relevant authority/person responsible and informs the person who submitted the report of this.

Investigation procedure: During the proceedings aimed at clarifying the matter, the officer for equal treatment organises meetings with the person who submitted the report and with the person alleged to have engaged in unequal treatment and with any other persons who possess information on the case. The equal treatment officer informs the person accused of unequal treatment about the nature of the allegations made and advises against any revenge action being taken. The person accused of unequal treatment is obliged to prove that s/he did not commit the alleged acts. After conducting investigatory proceedings, the equal treatment officer formulates recommendations for the rector on how to settle the matter. If the application concerns the rector, the recommendations are forwarded to the chairperson of the University Council.

Outcomes and time frame: If unequal treatment is ascertained to have occurred, the equal treatment officer may recommend that the perpetrator be punished and that the prosecutor's office be informed of the possibility that a crime has been committed. The equal treatment officer shall conduct the proceedings within one month of the date on which the application was filed or the case was initiated by the university. In cases that prove justified, the rector may appoint a Commission for Equal Treatment. The commission will conduct the procedure within one month or in the case of particularly complex cases within two months of the date on which it was appointed.

Additional information: The university has several other policies which are relevant for eradicating GBV. Those are the university strategy,¹⁴ internal anti-mobbing policy,¹⁵ a procedure for surveys among employees¹⁶ and the Gender Equality Plan (GEP).¹⁷ The GEP includes a thematic area 'Safe and friendly work and study environment. Building a culture of non-violence.' The objectives are to 'implement zero tolerance for violence and discrimination based on gender or gender identity' and 'inform on rights, obligations, and appropriate responses to violence and discrimination based on sex or gender identity'.

This document reflects the situation as of July 2022.

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¹⁴ Resolution No. 60 of the Senate of the Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toru of November 30, 2021. The strategy of the Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toru 20212026, available at: <https://strategia.umk.pl/pages/strategia/?lang=en>.

¹⁵ Order No. 13 of the Rector of the Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toru of February 11, 2016, on internal anti-mobbing policy at the Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toru, available at: <https://www.umk.pl/en/university/excellence-in-research/internal-regulations/Polityka-antymobbingowa-ZR-13-2016.pdf>.

¹⁶ Order No. 253 of the Rector of the Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toru of November 18, 2020, on the procedure of surveying employee satisfaction at the Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toru, available at: <https://www.wl.cm.umk.pl/panel/wp-content/uploads/Zarzadzenie-Nr-253-Rektora-Uniwersytetu-Mikolaja-Kopernika-w-Toruniu-z-dnia-18-listopada-2020-r.-w-sprawie-procedury-badania-satysfakcji-pracownikow-na-UMK.pdf>.

¹⁷ <https://www.umk.pl/en/university/excellence-in-research/internal-regulations/Gender-Equality-Plan-ZR-30-2022-Annex.pdf>

